

Diasporic Consciousness in Bharati Mukherjee's *Wife*

Dr. Dinesh P. Patil and Miss. Shiba Akhtar Khan

Appasaheb R. B. Garud Arts, Commerce, and Science College, Shendurni. Tal. Jamner.

Email ID: dinesh.p.patil@gmail.com, shibakhan0290@gmail.com

Abstract

This research paper explores diasporic consciousness through Bharati Mukherjee's novel *Wife*, which follows Dimple Dasgupta, a young Indian woman navigating the complex realities of immigration in the United States. It discusses how migration heightens issues of identity crisis, cultural displacement, alienation, and gendered oppression. The novel depicts the emotional and cultural confusions faced by immigrants, balancing inherited traditions with assimilation pressures in a foreign land. The analysis shows Mukherjee's portrayal of diasporic consciousness as a fragmented state characterized by alienation, identity struggles, and cultural disturbance. Dimple's attempt to reconcile her expectations of marriage, self-identity, and freedom with patriarchal constraints and racial marginalization reveals gendered aspects of the diaspora. The paper argues that Mukherjee depicts diasporic consciousness as a traumatic, dissonant process rather than a seamless cultural blend. Ultimately, the novel highlights the psychological pain of migration and questions the idealized notion of the American Dream for immigrant women.

Keywords: Immigration, Hyphenated Identity, Cultural Displacement, Expatriation, Alienation, Identity Crises.

Introduction

The term for the sense of alienation, nostalgia, and displacement among immigrants is diaspora, derived from the Latin word 'diasperian', meaning dispersion. Originally, it refers to the dispersion of Jews outside Israel. The Jews were forced to leave Jerusalem, their homeland, and thus they scattered across the world. This exodus led to the loss of their identity. Sunil Amrith, in his critical work, *Migration and Diaspora in South Asia*, explains that the term diaspora is "the dispersion or spread of any people from their original homeland" (pg. 57). James Clifford, in his work, *Routes: Travel and Translation in the Late Twentieth Century*, uses the phrase, "dwellings in displacement" (pg. 310). Since dwelling is

a key aspect of defining diaspora, the ideas of home and homemaking are essential in diasporic spaces.

Today, the term now encompasses ideas beyond its initial links to hostility, tragedy, alienation, loss, exile, and the aspiration to return. It also signifies a shared homeland—whether through voluntary or forced migration—and involves feelings of estrangement and marginalization within the host country. Vijay Agnew, a Social Science professor, describes diaspora in his book *Diaspora, Memory, and Identity* not just as the dispersal of people from a particular place but also as involving “the collective memory and trauma involved in such dispersion” (p. 193).

Even though the term ‘Diaspora’ has evolved in meaning over time, it still retains certain characteristics such as rootlessness, homelessness, alienation, and love for the homeland. Salman Rushdie, in his critical work, *Imaginary Homeland*, shares his personal experience as an expatriate, stating that:

“Exiles or emigrants or expatriates are haunted by some sense of loss, some urge to reclaim, to look back, even at the risk of being mutated into pillars of salt. If we do look back, we must also do so in the knowledge – which gives rise to profound uncertainties - that our physical alienation from India almost inevitably means that we will not be capable of reclaiming precisely the thing that was lost; that we will in short, create fictions, not actual cities or villages, but invisible ones, imaginary homelands, Indias of the mind” (pg.10).

In simple terms, when people leave their homes, they often feel lonely and are surprised by how much they miss the comfort of a real home. Connecting with a new culture can be naturally difficult. Differences in cultural and religious backgrounds often make it hard for individuals to find their identity. During the process of settling into a new environment, many diasporic communities experience psychological trauma. Even after adjusting, these communities often face discrimination, alienation, and identity struggles. Common themes in diasporic literature include feelings of displacement, loneliness, societal alienation, and longing.

P. Malikarjuna Rao states that "the lives of immigrants do not follow straight lines or smooth paths, as they are compelled to confront centuries of history within their lifetime, thereby having to endure the experiences of multiple lives and roles."

Homi K. Bhabha, in his book *The Location of Culture*, explores the idea of hyphenated identity. He affirms that “I am both a mixture of my home country and host country”. Through this critical work, Bhabha has discussed the concept of hybridity, which emerges when individuals from different cultural backgrounds come into contact. Bhabha emphasized that diaspora communities often inhabit a space of cultural interaction and negotiation, leading to hybrid identities that challenge fixed notions of belonging. He highlights the idea of ‘Third Space’, where new cultural meanings and identities are formed. Moreover, several other diasporic writers have penned down the plight of diasporic communities who suffered a lot to create their identity and adjust to their newfound world.

Diasporic Consciousness

Immigration

Immigration is frequently regarded as the best option for a better life, despite the challenges and difficulties that come with it. For most Asian immigrants, the United States was a "paradise on earth." C.L. Chua states that “Discovery of the American passage was a dream of fame and failure of egregious identity and material wealth”. (pg. 54). This land of golden opportunities lent a Midas touch for people entering this ‘Promised Land’. In the New Standard Encyclopaedia, the United States is referred to as “a Melting Pot” and “a nation of nations” (pg. 41). All immigrants must, however, go through the process of becoming adopted, Americanized, and integrated into the country's social and economic structure.

Dimple's joy is beyond words when Amit reveals that they will be moving to the United States. She gets ready nicely and realizes that everything she needs for a new life is there. Over the phone, Dimple informs her closest friend, Dixie, that she will not be taking any of her old saris with her to America. Relics from Dimple's past are something she does not want to keep around. Dimple finds being a mother to be a burden. In self-induced abortion, Dimple appears to use abortion as a means of venting her wrath against the Basu family while also assuming control over her body, signifying her mastery over it. She dislikes being directed by her husband and being subject to Basus' authority. Dimple is excited to move to a place where she won't have to deal with the demands of domesticity, where she won't have to live under Basu's rule or domestication, and where she can be herself.

Dimple might look for ways to escape the role that her community assigns to a wife in America. Her goal is to investigate ways to deviate from the pattern created for middle-class Indian women. She makes friends with Ina Mullick, who she believes broke the traditional expectations of an Indian bride and embraced American culture.

Identity Crisis

Dimple had dreamed since she was a young girl that marriage would give her all the luxuries in the world, but she is now unhappy and disgusted with the circumstances she has found herself in after getting married. To be considered a proper wife by societal standards, she first had to give up her name and then change her way of life. Because of her dark complexion and Bengali name, Dimple finds Amit's mother, Mrs. Basu, and his older sister, Mrs. Ghosh, repulsive at their first meeting. Mrs. Basu then changes Dimple's name to Nandini because she doesn't like it. Dimple was hesitant but did not oppose, and she couldn't say anything because she wanted to build a strong relationship with her mother-in-law.

Earlier, Dimple was so excited to go to America and start a new journey. Still, after moving to America, it became tough for her to establish her own identity there. Fakrul Alam states that, 'It is quite obvious, then, that Dimple has come to America, ready to be transformed and willing to seek out an identity that would take her away from her South Asian Community or connect with mainstream American society' (pg.41). Dimple is helplessly caught in her quest for a female identity as an immigrant. She wants to be like Ina Mullick, who has made her own identity as 'more American than Americans'. Dimple is so fascinated by Ina and her American ways. But it was tough for her to fully become an American because of the language barrier. She was also unable to operate the elevators. To gain a new American identity, she indulges in an affair with an American, Milt.

Hyphenated Identity

Homi K. Bhabha, in his book *The Location of Culture*, explores the idea of hyphenated identity. He affirms that "I am both a mixture of my home country and host country". Through this critical work, Bhabha has discussed the concept of hybridity, which emerges when individuals from different cultural backgrounds come into contact. Bhabha emphasized that diaspora communities often inhabit a space of cultural interaction and negotiation, leading to hybrid identities that challenge fixed notions of belonging. He highlights the idea of 'Third Space', where new cultural meanings and identities are formed.

When Dimple goes to the party in Manhattan, she meets various immigrants from all over the world. They show her different ways that being Indian and being American are connected. She hears about Ina Mullick, a Bengali wife whose careless husband allowed her to become “more American than the Americans” (pg. 10). Bharati Mukherjee illustrates the influence of American ways through the character of Ina Mullick, who represents assimilation. Ina has accepted American ways and attitudes, adapting to American culture, food, clothing, and language.

Cultural Displacement.

Cultural displacement refers to the feeling of dislocation that people experience when their cultural identity is challenged or undermined, especially due to migration, globalization, or societal changes. Shyam M. Asani, in his critical work ‘Identity Crises in The Nowhere Man and Wife,’ states that ‘Dimple is entrapped in a dilemma of tensions between American culture society and the traditional constraints surrounding an Indian wife, between a feminist desire to be assertive and independent and the Indian need to be submissive and self-effacing’ (pg. 42). Because she partially accepts both American and Indian cultures, she becomes frustrated and develops neurosis, which leads her to commit destructive acts such as sin, murder, or suicide. The root of her mental disorder is that she was uprooted from her family and homeland. Amit wants Dimple to be a good Bengali wife who takes care of her home and husband and learns how to live in America without becoming too Americanized, which makes her all the more frustrated.

Expatriation

Expatriation is the process of leaving one’s home country to live in another, often for a long time or permanently. It happens for many reasons, such as work, education, personal relationships, or a desire for a different lifestyle. Expatriation is common in developed countries. Christine Gomez, in her work, ‘The Ongoing Quest of Bharati Mukherjee from Expatriation to Immigration,’ provides a clear definition of the term expatriation.

“Expatriation is a complex state of mind and emotion, which includes wistful longing for the past, often symbolized by the ancestral home, the pain of exile and homelessness, the struggle to maintain the difference between oneself and the new, unfriendly surroundings, an assumption of moral and cultural superiority over the host country and a refusal to accept the identity forced one by the environment. The expatriate builds a cocoon around

herself/himself as a refuge from the cultural dilemmas and the experienced hostility or unfriendliness in the new country. (pg. 72)

Through the characters of Jyoti and Meena Sen, Bharati Mukherjee illustrates expatriation. Because America is a land of opportunities, the couple travelled to America to earn money. For Jyoti, America was solely a place of wealth. He aimed to make a lot of money, then return to his hometown and build a home, which would have cost him about five lakhs, and thus become the 'Maharaj of Lower Circular Road' (pg.9).

When Dimple and Amit arrived in America, they were received by the Sen family. Dimple was very excited to explore America and embark on a new journey, and thus she is very eager to see the Sen's house. As they reached their house, Dimple was very astonished to see it, which was a typical Indian house. It is exactly like a common Indian house in Calcutta. Jyoti's American house is very Indian-like, with no chairs in the room, but only a mat and a rug are served to guests. Jyoti's house makes Amit comfortable because he feels no difference between his house in Calcutta and Jyoti's house. This indicates that the Sen couple is living abroad in America and aspires to return home once they have saved enough money.

Alienation

According to the Stanford Encyclopaedia of Philosophy, the concept of alienation identifies a distinct kind of psychological or social ill, namely, one involving a problematic separation between a self and others that belong together. Cetin et al. have explained that alienation expresses that the individual has a decreased adaptation to the social, cultural, and natural environment, loses her/his control over the environment, and becomes isolated by getting gradually helpless.

Dimple and her community of expatriates experience alienation in a country whose ways they cannot understand. Before Dimple had ever set foot in America, she had friends remark that even though it's a place to have a lot of fun, one must endure being a foreigner forever.

Before going to America Dimple has been invited in a farewell party sponsored by her friend, Dixie, in that party one of the guests has apprise that, "You may think of it as immigration, my dear...but what you are is a resident alien" (pg.46). When Dimple arrived in New York, she has been informed by Meena Sen that, she feels as an outsider because it was tough to understand American humors and the American language. Earlier, Dimple felt that

she was now free from all the clutches of Indian traditions, and she was not obliged to follow the role of a traditional Indian wife. But gradually she feels alienated as it becomes difficult for her to learn American ways and living standards, language becomes one of the obstacles for her to interact with the people around her, and thus she becomes frustrated with not knowing English. When Amit got a job, the couple shifted to an apartment, where she feels alienated, as most of the time she has to be alone in the apartment. She has to spend her time watching television, soap operas, and murder mysteries. Meanwhile, she indulges in an affair with a white man named Milt, with whom she feels safe and protected. Once, after returning from a function with Milt, Dimple feels, “the inhuman maze of New York became as safe and simple as Ballygunge” (pg. 196). When they were together at her apartment, he promised Dimple to protect her, but as he left, she again felt lonelier than ever.

Conclusion

In *Wife*, Bharati Mukherjee presents diaspora not as a simple story of migration and opportunity, but as a deeply unsettling psychological rupture. Through Dimple Dasgupta’s experiences, the novel exposes the emotional dislocation, cultural alienation, and identity fragmentation faced by immigrants caught between inherited traditions and an unfamiliar host culture. Dimple’s inability to reconcile her expectations of marriage, freedom, and selfhood with the realities of diasporic life reveals how migration can intensify inner conflicts rather than resolve them. The American dream, instead of offering liberation, becomes a site of isolation and despair. Ultimately, *Wife* suggests that diaspora, when marked by silence, patriarchal constraints, and cultural dissonance, can erode the self. Mukherjee thus critiques the romanticized notion of migration and highlights the urgent need for emotional anchoring and self-definition within the diasporic experience.

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